

Salmonella control programme in accordance with Regulation (EC) No. 2160/2003: results for the year 2011

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The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) has assessed data on the presence (prevalence) of salmonella in breeding poultry, broiler and turkey populations since 2008. It publishes its results each year. These reports are part of the EU-wide salmonella control programme. They are based on results from both the official sampling and own checks conducted by companies.

The analysed data from the year 2011 document that compared to the preceding year, salmonella was detected in fewer production animal populations: for breeding hens, broilers as well as breeding and fattening turkeys, a prevalence of below 1 % was found for the control-relevant serovars. For laying hens, 2.2 % of the flocks tested salmonella positive, i.e. 0.4 % less than in the year 2010. This means that in Germany, the agreed EU goals for the reduction of salmonella presence was reached for all poultry groups covered by the control programme.

The full version of this BfR Opinion is available in German on <http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/salmonella-bekaempfungsprogramm-gemaess-verordnung-eg-nr-2160-2003-ergebnisse-fuer-2011.pdf>